

Inversion of loading-implicit adsorption isotherms by means of the Lambert W function

Giani de Vargas Brião^a and Khim Hoong Chu^{b,*}

^a School of Chemical Engineering, University of Campinas (UNICAMP), Cidade Universitária Zeferino Vaz, 13083-852, Campinas, São Paulo, Brazil

^b Honeychem Research, Newtown, Wellington 6021, New Zealand

*Corresponding author.

E-mail: khimchu@gmail.com (K.H. Chu)

Journal of Chemical Technology and Biotechnology. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jctb.7189>

ABSTRACT

BACKGROUND: Simple isotherm models such as the Langmuir and Freundlich equations are frequently used to correlate water contaminant adsorption data. In the conventional data fitting approach, the Langmuir and Freundlich equations are fitted to experimental data by minimizing the difference between the measured and calculated adsorbed phase concentrations. However, some isotherm equations are implicit in adsorbed phase concentration. Such isotherms must be converted to explicit forms to allow the use of standard nonlinear regression methods in data correlation. This paper explores the use of the Lambert W function to invert the loading-implicit isotherms of Elovich, Volmer, and Jossens to solve for adsorbed phase concentration as a function of liquid phase concentration.

RESULTS: The inverted Elovich, Volmer, and Jossens isotherms were fitted to literature adsorption data of water contaminants using the standard nonlinear regression procedure in Excel. Data fitting was accomplished by making use of a freely available Excel add-in and a highly accurate analytical approximation to evaluate the Lambert W function. The inverted isotherms were tested against the experimental isotherms of cobalt, uranium, and cephalosporin C. In all cases studied, satisfactory fits were obtained, validating the practicability of the proposed data fitting approach.

CONCLUSIONS: The loading-implicit Elovich, Volmer, and Jossens isotherms can be formulated as loading-explicit equations in terms of the Lambert W function, allowing the use of conventional least-squares fitting procedures in data correlation. The practical implementation of the Lambert W function in Excel provides a novel method to fit loading-implicit isotherms to experimental data of water contaminants.

Keywords: implicit isotherm; Lambert W function; Elovich; Volmer; Jossens

INTRODUCTION

The adsorption of water contaminants by porous materials is difficult to predict from first principles because it is affected by a variety of factors such as temperature, pH, and ionic strength. As a consequence, experimental determinations of adsorption equilibrium and kinetics are almost always necessary. In practice, the acquisition of water contaminant equilibrium isotherms is commonly carried out by batch methods. In most cases, type I equilibrium isotherms have been observed, although isotherms of types II-V have also been reported.

Experimentally measured isotherms for water contaminant adsorption on solid materials are generally correlated using suitable theoretical or empirical models. Commonly used isotherm models include the equations of Langmuir, Freundlich, Sips, and Dubinin–Radushkevich.^{1–3} Many software packages, including Excel,⁴ offer standard nonlinear regression methods to fit these isotherm equations to experimental data. The conventional nonlinear regression procedure minimizes the sum of squared residuals (SSR) using a fitting algorithm. The most common SSR, given here by Eqn (1), is defined as the difference between the measured and calculated adsorbed phase concentrations. In Eqn (1), $q_{i,obs}$ is the i th observed adsorbed phase concentration, $q_{i,fit}$ is the i th adsorbed phase concentration calculated from the chosen isotherm equation, and m is the number of data points.

$$SSR = \sum_{i=1}^m (q_{i,obs} - q_{i,fit})^2 \quad (1)$$

The aforementioned isotherm equations (Langmuir, Freundlich, Sips, and Dubinin–Radushkevich) are explicit in q , i.e., q can be isolated and placed on the left side of these equations ($q = f(c)$, where f is a known isotherm function and c is the liquid phase concentration). For these loading-explicit isotherms, it is straightforward to use Eqn (1) as the objective function in least-squares fitting because $q_{i,fit}$ in Eqn (1) can be easily calculated. However, several isotherm equations used to describe water contaminant adsorption are implicit in q , i.e., q appears on both sides of the equations because it is not possible to isolate and place it on the left side ($q = f(q,c)$). A notable example is the Frumkin–Fowler–Guggenheim isotherm. Consequently, to fit a loading-implicit isotherm with Eqn (1) as the objective function, it is necessary to implement an iterative scheme (bisection or Newton–Raphson) within the fitting algorithm to calculate $q_{i,fit}$ at each iteration. This may be somewhat cumbersome to implement in Excel. The additional numerical step can be avoided if Eqn (2) is used as the objective function in the least-squares fitting of a loading-implicit isotherm.^{5–8} In Eqn (2), $c_{i,obs}$ is the i th observed solution phase concentration and $c_{i,fit}$ is the i th solution phase concentration

calculated from the chosen isotherm. Because most loading-implicit isotherms can be expressed as equations explicit in c ($c = f(q)$), Eqn (2) can be used in lieu of Eqn (1) in the least-squares fitting of such isotherms.

$$SSR = \sum_{i=1}^m (c_{i,obs} - c_{i,fit})^2 \quad (2)$$

In addition to the least-squares fitting approach based on Eqn (2), a regression technique called orthogonal distance regression has recently been used to fit the loading-implicit Frumkin–Fowler–Guggenheim isotherm to adsorption data.⁹ This paper describes a different method of handling loading-implicit isotherms in the correlation of equilibrium data. The inversion of three loading-implicit isotherms (Elovich, Volmer, and Jossens) is achieved by means of a mathematical technique based on the Lambert W function. These three loading-implicit isotherms were selected for this research because their mathematical forms are amenable to treatment by the Lambert W function. The resulting isotherm expressions, explicit in q , allow the use of Eqn (1) as the objective function in standard nonlinear regression. Given that there is no built-in Lambert W function in Excel, the secondary aim of this work is to illustrate how the Lambert W function can be evaluated within Excel using a freely available add-in and an analytical approximation.

There are several applications of the Lambert W function in chemical engineering. A 2012 review describes the use of the Lambert W function in biochemical kinetics, especially enzyme-catalyzed reaction kinetics.¹⁰ A very recent article illustrates how the Lambert W function can help provide solutions to a number of problems of interest to chemical engineers.¹¹ Most of the case studies examined in these two reports^{10,11} used the Lambert W function to convert implicit algebraic equations into explicit forms. In the field of adsorption research, the Lambert W function was used to invert an implicit kinetic model of multilayer adsorption.¹² The inversion of loading-implicit adsorption isotherms by means of the Lambert W function has not attracted much attention. The research described in the present study fills this gap.

THEORY

Loading-implicit isotherms

Various adsorption isotherm models have been repeatedly reviewed in the environmental adsorption literature.^{13–18} Although these reviews list one or more loading-implicit isotherms, none provide guidance on their application in data correlation. In this work, the loading-implicit isotherms of Elovich, Volmer, and Jossens are evaluated against experimental data taken from the literature of adsorptive water remediation.

A modified form of Langmuir's kinetic argument for saturable adsorption of gases to solid surfaces was used to derive the Elovich isotherm, given here by Eqn (3).^{19,20} In Eqn (3), k_E is an equilibrium constant while q_E is the apparent saturation capacity. A linear form of the Elovich isotherm is commonly used to correlate water contaminant adsorption data.

$$c = \frac{1}{k_E} \frac{q}{q_E} \exp\left(\frac{q}{q_E}\right) \quad (3)$$

Like the Langmuir adsorption theory, the Volmer adsorption theory²¹ has the following assumptions: (1) adsorption is reversible; (2) adsorption is restricted to a monolayer; (3) the solid surface is homogeneous; and (4) there is no lateral interaction between adsorbed molecules. The difference between the Volmer theory and the Langmuir theory is that the former assumes that the adsorbed molecules are not localized in space. The Volmer isotherm is given by Eqn (4), where k_V is an equilibrium constant and q_V is the apparent saturation capacity. The exponential term accounts for the mobility of the adsorbed molecules. A nonlinear regression method incorporating a numerical step was recently used to fit the loading-implicit Volmer isotherm to experimental data.²²

$$c = \frac{1}{k_V} \frac{q}{q_V - q} \exp\left(\frac{q}{q_V - q}\right) \quad (4)$$

The Jossens isotherm is given by Eqn (5), where h_J and k_J are constants that depend on temperature, and n_J is a fitting parameter. The Jossens isotherm describes adsorption on heterogeneous surfaces and satisfies Henry's law at low concentrations. It has been claimed that the Jossens isotherm can be derived from thermodynamics.²³

$$c = \frac{q}{h_J} \exp(k_J q^{n_J}) \quad (5)$$

As presented in Eqns (3)–(5), the three isotherms are explicit in c . It is obvious that q cannot be expressed explicitly.

Lambert W Function

The Lambert W function, named after Johann Heinrich Lambert,²⁴ is also known as the omega function or product logarithm. It occurs frequently in mathematics and physics. Its characteristics, including numerical algorithms for its calculation, have been extensively studied in the mathematical literature.²⁵ The Lambert W function, denoted by $W(x)$, represents solutions of Eqn (6), that is, $y = W(x)$.

$$y \exp(y) = x \quad (6)$$

The real-valued Lambert W function is defined on the interval $(-\exp(-1), \infty)$ and ranges from minus infinity to plus infinity. For all real $x \geq 0$, it has exactly one real solution: $y = W_0(x)$. For real x where $-\exp(-1) < x < 0$, it has exactly two real solutions: $y = W_0(x)$ and $y = W_{-1}(x)$. The Lambert W function is plotted in Fig. 1, where its two branches, $W_0(x)$ and $W_{-1}(x)$, are identified. The lower or negative branch $W_{-1}(x)$ is indicated by the dashed line, while the upper or principal branch $W_0(x)$ is depicted by the solid line. Figure 2 compares the principal branch to the logarithmic function. It is noteworthy that the Lambert W function goes through the $(0,0)$ origin while the natural logarithm is undefined at $x = 0$. Since the Lambert W function cannot be expressed in terms of other elementary functions, numerical methods are used to evaluate $W(x)$. It has been implemented in several commercial software packages such as MATLAB, Maple, Mathematica, and Mathcad, all of which use iterative algorithms to evaluate $W(x)$ with pre-defined precision.

Figure 1. Branches of the Lambert W function. The lower or negative branch $W_{-1}(x)$ is given by the dashed line and the upper or principal branch $W_0(x)$ is denoted by the solid line.

Figure 2. Comparison of the Lambert W function and natural logarithm.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The primary aim of the present study is to demonstrate how the Lambert W function can be used to convert the loading-implicit Elovich, Volmer, and Jossens isotherms to expressions explicit in q , which will allow the direct use of the SSR defined by Eqn (1) as the objective function in the least-squares fitting of experimental data. We will discuss these three isotherms in sequence.

The Elovich isotherm

The Elovich isotherm given by Eqn (3) was originally devised to describe aqueous phase adsorption.^{19,20} It has been used to correlate the adsorption isotherms for a diverse array of water contaminants.²⁶ The two-parameter Elovich isotherm is frequently rearranged into a linear form (Eqn (7)) to facilitate parameter estimation by linear regression. If Eqn (7) is obeyed, a plot of its left-side member against q should yield a straight line.

$$\ln\left(\frac{q}{c}\right) = \ln(k_E q_E) - \frac{1}{q_E} q \quad (7)$$

Recently, Patil et al.²⁷ applied the linearized Elovich equation to the isotherm data for cobalt adsorption on an activated carbon adsorbent. The cobalt data set, shown in Fig. 3, is of type I form. The linear fit of Eqn (7) was not satisfactory, returning an R^2 score of 0.92. Here, we will convert the loading-implicit Elovich isotherm (Eqn (3)) to an explicit form and fit the resulting expression to the cobalt adsorption data. Inverting the loading-implicit Elovich isotherm by means of the Lambert W function is quite straightforward. First, Eqn (3) is expressed as Eqn (8). It is evident that Eqn (8) is analogous to Eqn (6) with $q/q_E = y$ and $k_{EC} = x$. It follows that the solution of Eqn (8) in terms of the Lambert W function is given by $y = W(x)$, which is rewritten as Eqn (9).

$$\frac{q}{q_E} \exp\left(\frac{q}{q_E}\right) = k_E c \quad (8)$$

$$q = q_E W(k_E c) \quad (9)$$

Because Eqn (9) is explicit in q , it can be fitted to the cobalt adsorption data in Fig. 3 using Eqn (1) as the objective function. Since x or k_{EC} is positive or zero, the $W(x)$ term in Eqn (9) corresponds to the principal branch $W_0(x)$ for $x \geq 0$. As noted above, the Lambert W function is available in several specialist software packages such as MATLAB and Maple, but not Excel. In this work, two methods are used to evaluate $W(x)$ in Excel, the first of which is an analytical approximation developed by Barry et al.²⁸ The analytical approximation given by Eqn (10) has a maximum relative error of less than 0.2% and can be used for $x > 0$. Although Eqn (10) is undefined at $x = 0$, the relative error at near-zero values of x is very small. For $x < 0$, analytical approximations for the principal branch $W_0(x)$ and the negative branch $W_{-1}(x)$ are also available in the work of Barry et al.²⁸

$$y \approx 1.45869 \ln\left\{\frac{1.2x}{\ln\left[2.4x/\ln(1+2.4x)\right]}\right\} - 0.45869 \ln\left[\frac{2x}{\ln(1+2x)}\right] \quad (10)$$

Equation (11) is another useful approximation of the Lambert W function.²⁹ It approximates $W(x)$ with a maximum relative error of less than 2% and can be used for $x > 0$.

$$y \approx \ln(1+x) \left\{ 1 - \frac{\ln[1 + \ln(1+x)]}{2 + \ln(1+x)} \right\} \quad (11)$$

The second method of $W(x)$ calculation makes use of an Excel add-in file developed by Scheuerell.³⁰ It is available for download from <https://github.com/mdscheuerell/Lambert-W-in-Excel>. In the Excel add-in file, $W(x)$ is approximated numerically from Eqn (12) ($y = W(x)$) using a root finding scheme based on the Halley iteration method. The two methods of $W(x)$ evaluation are summarized in Table 1.

$$y_{j+1} = y_j - \frac{y_j \exp(y_j) - x}{(y_j + 1) \exp(y_j) - \frac{1}{2} \frac{(y_j + 2)}{(y_j + 1)} [y_j \exp(y_j) - x]} \quad (12)$$

Table 1. Two methods of $W(x)$ evaluation in Excel

Method	$W(x)$ calculation
1. Analytical approximation ²⁸	Eqn (10)
2. Excel add-in ³⁰	Eqn (12)

The inverted Elovich isotherm given by Eqn (9) was fitted to the cobalt data using the generalized reduced gradient algorithm provided in Excel's Solver and the two methods of $W(x)$ evaluation described in Table 1. The resulting parameter estimates and R^2 values obtained by the two regression methods are practically identical, as can be seen in the first and second row entries in Table 2. For comparison, a nonlinear least-squares fitting of Eqn (9) to the cobalt data was also conducted using Mathematica, which uses the command `ProductLog` to evaluate $W(x)$. The resulting parameter estimates and R^2 value (third row entry, Table 2) are identical to those obtained using Excel and method 2 to evaluate $W(x)$ (second row entry, Table 2). This comparison validates the accuracy of the two methods of $W(x)$ evaluation in Excel. Figure 3 shows that the loading-explicit Elovich fit is in excellent conformity with the experimental cobalt isotherm. The fitted curve was calculated using the k_E and q_E estimates of method 1 (first row entry, Table 2).

Table 2. Loading-explicit Elovich fits (Eqn (9)) of the cobalt adsorption data plotted in Fig. 3

Software	$W(x)$ calculation	k_E (L mg ⁻¹)	q_E (mg g ⁻¹)	R^2
Excel	Method 1, Table 1	0.351	66.70	0.983
Excel	Method 2, Table 1	0.353	66.47	0.983
Mathematica	ProductLog command	0.353	66.47	0.983

Figure 4. Comparison of linearized Elovich fit (Eqn (7)) and cobalt adsorption data.²⁷

As mentioned, the experimental cobalt isotherm in the original paper²⁷ was analyzed using the linear form of the Elovich isotherm given by Eqn (7). Figure 4 shows the use of linear regression to fit Eqn (7) to the cobalt isotherm data. The linear regression results are $k_E = 0.523$ L mg⁻¹, $q_E = 59.17$ mg g⁻¹, and $R^2 = 0.922$. Figure 4 shows that the transformed data does not exhibit a linear trend, resulting in a rather unsatisfactory linear fit. In addition, there are significant differences between the estimates of k_E and q_E obtained by the linear fit and those produced by the nonlinear fits (Table 2). This finding supports the notion that data correlation using a linear version of an inherently nonlinear adsorption model tends to produce inferior results. Nevertheless, the linearized Elovich isotherm is frequently used to correlate water contaminant isotherms, as can be seen in some recent publications.^{31–33}

In a recent article, the Elovich isotherm, written in the form of Eqn (13), was used to fit the experimental isotherms for uranium(VI) adsorption on two adsorbents (leonardite and humic acid derived from leonardite).³⁴ Equation (13) is, of course, just a rearranged form of Eqn (3).

$$q = k_E q_E \exp\left(-\frac{q}{q_E}\right) c \quad (13)$$

Figure 5(a), taken from the original study, shows the fits of the Elovich isotherm to the uranium(VI) adsorption data.³⁴ The filled symbols represent the isotherms for uranium(VI) adsorption on the humic acid adsorbent, and the hollow symbols denote the isotherms for uranium(VI) adsorption on the leonardite adsorbent. As can be seen in Fig. 5(a), the reported Elovich fits (lines) were very poor, failing to track the hyperbolic shapes of the experimental isotherms. The original study³⁴ did not provide any information on the regression method used to fit the Elovich isotherm given by Eqn (13) to the uranium(VI) adsorption data. Here, the loading-explicit Elovich isotherm (Eqn (9)) was fitted to the uranium(VI) adsorption data using Excel and method 1 (Table 1) to evaluate $W(x)$. Figure 5(b) shows that the entire hyperbolic profiles of the experimental isotherms represented by the filled symbols are well described by the loading-explicit Elovich isotherm. For clarity, the fitting results for the experimental isotherms denoted by the hollow symbols are not shown in Fig. 5(b). The exceedingly poor performance of the Elovich isotherm depicted in Fig. 5(a) is most likely due to the use of defective data regression methods.

Figure 5. (a) Comparison of Elovich fits (Eqn (13)) and uranium(VI) adsorption data. Figure reproduced with permission from Meng et al.³⁴ Copyright 2021 American Chemical Society. (b) Comparison of loading-explicit Elovich fits (Eqn (9)) and uranium(VI) adsorption data (this work).

The Volmer isotherm

Two review articles^{16,18} have featured the Volmer isotherm²¹ (Eqn (4)) without pointing out that it is implicit in q . Like the Elovich isotherm, it is straightforward to formulate the Volmer isotherm as an expression explicit in q . Rearranging Eqn (4) yields Eqn (14), which is in the

form of Eqn (6) with $q/(q_V - q) = y$ and $k_V c = x$. Consequently, the solution of Eqn (14) is given by $y = W(x)$, which is rewritten as Eqn (15). Because the product $k_V c$ is positive or zero, $W(k_V c)$ corresponds to the principal branch $W_0(x)$ for $x \geq 0$. As such, one can use the analytical approximation given by Eqn (10) or the Excel add-in based on Eqn (12) to calculate $W(k_V c)$.

$$\frac{q}{q_V - q} \exp\left(\frac{q}{q_V - q}\right) = k_V c \quad (14)$$

$$q = q_V \left[\frac{W(k_V c)}{1 + W(k_V c)} \right] \quad (15)$$

To evaluate the data fitting ability of the loading-explicit Volmer isotherm, Eqn (15) was fitted to the cobalt data depicted in Fig. 3 using method 1 (Table 1) to evaluate $W(x)$. Referring to Fig. 6, it is evident that the agreement between the Volmer isotherm fit and cobalt data is satisfactory ($R^2 = 0.979$). The fitted curve was calculated from Eqn (15) with $k_V = 0.038 \text{ L mg}^{-1}$ and $q_V = 320.29 \text{ mg g}^{-1}$.

Figure 6. Comparison of loading-explicit Volmer fit (Eqn (15)) and cobalt adsorption data.²⁷

Figure 7. Comparison of Volmer fit (Eqn (4), solid line) and cephalosporin C adsorption data.¹⁸ The dotted line was calculated from Eqn (4) using the values of k_V and q_V reported in the original study.¹⁸ The dashed line was calculated from Eqn (4) by swapping the values of k_V and q_V reported in the original study.¹⁸

The Volmer isotherm was recently used to correlate the experimental isotherm for cephalosporin C adsorption on aged polystyrene.¹⁸ Excel's Solver was used to fit the Volmer isotherm given by Eqn (4), which is explicit in c , to the cephalosporin C data by minimizing the SSR defined by Eqn (2), yielding $k_V = 0.757 \text{ L mg}^{-1}$ and $q_V = 1.862 \text{ mg g}^{-1}$. This data fitting

procedure was repeated in the present study, resulting in $k_V = 1.726 \text{ L mg}^{-1}$ and $q_V = 0.763 \text{ mg g}^{-1}$. The fitted curve, depicted by the solid line in Fig. 7, shows large deviations at low concentrations. Also shown in the figure is the fitted curve of the original study (dotted line),¹⁸ calculated using the original parameter estimates. It is clear that the values of q_V and k_V reported in the original study are erroneous; the two numbers should be swapped in order to produce a curve similar to our fitted curve, as shown by the dashed line in Fig. 7.

When the cephalosporin C data set is plotted in the conventional q vs c manner, it reveals a sigmoid or type V isotherm shape, as can be seen in Fig. 8. Because the mathematical form of the Volmer isotherm is confined to describing hyperbolic or type I isotherm shapes, it cannot represent the sigmoid or S-shaped isotherm of cephalosporin C. To correlate the cephalosporin C isotherm, one should use an isotherm model with the correct functional form. Examples of such models can be found in the work of Inglezakis et al.³⁵ Figure 8 depicts the fit of one such isotherm model, known as the Krishnamurti equation, which is based on a cooperative adsorption mechanism.^{36,37} With a near-perfect R^2 score of 0.999, the Krishnamurti isotherm is shown to surpass the Volmer isotherm in tracking the sigmoid shape of the cephalosporin C data. As mentioned, the Volmer isotherm is incapable of generating sigmoid curves.

Figure 8. Comparison of Volmer fit, Krishnamurti fit, and cephalosporin C adsorption data.¹⁸

The Jossens isotherm

This isotherm is a three-parameter expression capable of representing type I isotherms.²³ It is sometimes referred to as the Myers isotherm.^{6,7,38-45} It should also be noted that the Redlich-Peterson isotherm was mistakenly referred to as the Jossens isotherm in some papers published in the 1980s.^{46,47} This misattribution can still be found in some recent studies.⁴⁸⁻⁵² The Jossens

isotherm defined by Eqn (5) has been used by several researchers to correlate liquid phase^{5-8,38-45,53-58} and gas phase⁵⁹⁻⁶¹ adsorption data since the 1980s. Least-squares fitting methods were used to estimate the three parameters of the Jossens isotherm. Some studies mentioned that the objective function was based on the SSR given by Eqn (2).⁵⁻⁸ An attempt was made to linearize the Jossens isotherm by assigning a fixed value to n_j .⁶² This linear approach was recently used by Bayuo et al.⁶³

In the present study, we will use the Lambert W function to convert the loading-implicit Jossens isotherm to a loading-explicit form. The isotherm equation obtained will be fitted to the cobalt adsorption data (Fig. 3). To invert the loading-implicit Jossens isotherm to solve for q , we will follow the method used by Kesisoglou et al.¹¹ to invert an implicit h -index function. The first step is to rearrange Eqn (5) as follows:

$$q \exp(k_j q^{n_j}) = h_j c \quad (16)$$

Taking the logarithm of both sides of the preceding equation gives Eqn (17).

$$\ln(q) + k_j q^{n_j} = \ln(h_j c) \quad (17)$$

We define a new equation:

$$z = k_j q^{n_j} \quad (18)$$

Taking the logarithm of both sides of the last result yields Eqn (19).

$$\ln(q) = \frac{1}{n_j} \ln(z) - \frac{1}{n_j} \ln(k_j) \quad (19)$$

Substituting Eqns (18) and (19) into Eqn (17) gives Eqn (20).

$$\frac{1}{n_j} \ln(z) - \frac{1}{n_j} \ln(k_j) + z = \ln(h_j c) \quad (20)$$

After simplifying and rearranging the preceding equation, we obtain Eqn (21).

$$\ln(z) + n_j z = \ln \left[k_j (h_j c)^{n_j} \right] \quad (21)$$

Taking the exponential of both sides of the last result gives Eqn (22).

$$z \exp(n_j z) = k_j (h_j c)^{n_j} \quad (22)$$

Multiplying both sides of Eqn (22) by n_j , we obtain Eqn (23), which is analogous to Eqn (6) with $n_j z = y$ and $n_j k_j (h_j c)^{n_j} = x$. The solution of Eqn (23) is thus given by $y = W(x)$, which can be written as Eqn (24).

$$n_j z \exp(n_j z) = n_j k_j (h_j c)^{n_j} \quad (23)$$

$$z = \frac{1}{n_J} W \left[n_J k_J (h_J c)^{n_J} \right] \quad (24)$$

Finally, substituting Eqn (18) into the preceding equation yields Eqn (25), which is the Jossens isotherm explicit in q .

$$q = \left\{ \frac{1}{n_J k_J} W \left[n_J k_J (h_J c)^{n_J} \right] \right\}^{1/n_J} \quad (25)$$

As before, the argument of $W(x)$ in Eqn (25) cannot be negative, allowing the use of the analytical approximation (Eqn (10)) to evaluate $W(x)$. Using method 1 (Table 1) to calculate $W(x)$, Eqn (25) was fitted to the cobalt adsorption data (Fig. 3) by minimizing the SSR defined by Eqn (1). Figure 9 shows the fitted curve of Eqn (25), calculated with $h_J = 49.17 \text{ L g}^{-1}$, $k_J = 0.089 \text{ mg}^{-n_J} \text{ g}^{n_J}$, and $n_J = 0.702$. It is clear from Fig. 9 that the Jossens isotherm fit manifests satisfactory agreement with the cobalt adsorption data, returning an R^2 score of 0.984.

Figure 9. Comparison of loading-explicit Jossens fit (Eqn (25)) and cobalt adsorption data.²⁷

Comparison of isotherms

The R^2 values for the fits of the Elovich ($R^2 = 0.983$), Volmer ($R^2 = 0.979$), and Jossens ($R^2 = 0.984$) isotherms to the cobalt adsorption data are very similar, indicating that their data fitting abilities are comparable. It is thus not possible to rank the three isotherms according to the R^2 metric. Another option for model comparison is the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) test,⁶⁴ which penalizes models with multiple adjustable parameters. For models with the same number of fitting parameters, comparing the AIC metric is equivalent to comparing the SSR. Given that the Jossens isotherm has three adjustable parameters while the Elovich and Volmer isotherms have two, the AIC test is more appropriate than the simple R^2 measure to compare

the three isotherms. According to the AIC test, the Akaike weights for the Elovich, Volmer, and Jossens isotherms are, respectively, 0.698, 0.276, and 0.026. The definition of the Akaike weight can be found in the book by Motulsky and Christopoulos.⁶⁵ Briefly, the model with the largest Akaike weight among a cohort of competing models receives the best support from the data at hand. Therefore, for the cobalt data set, the Elovich isotherm with the largest Akaike weight is the best performing isotherm model in this group of three competing isotherms.

Because type I isotherm shapes can be described accurately by a two-parameter isotherm, using an isotherm with more than two free parameters to fit such data is unlikely to yield a significant improvement in the goodness of fit. It is therefore not surprising that the three-parameter Jossens isotherm with the smallest Akaike weight is the worst performing isotherm model according to the AIC test, although its R^2 score is comparable to that of the Elovich isotherm.

As a point of interest, the two-parameter Langmuir and Freundlich isotherms were fitted to the cobalt data set to see if they could outperform the Elovich isotherm. The least-squares fitting of the cobalt data by Excel with Eqn (1) as the objective function returned an identical R^2 score of 0.976 for both isotherms, which is slightly inferior to that of the Elovich isotherm. With five competing isotherms, the descending order of the Akaike weight is the following: Elovich (0.549) > Volmer (0.217) > Langmuir (0.113) > Freundlich (0.101) > Jossens (0.020). It seems that the Elovich isotherm is highly competitive against the Langmuir and Freundlich isotherms in correlating the type I cobalt isotherm. It should be noted that the Elovich isotherm, like the Freundlich isotherm, does not predict an adsorption maximum. Therefore, it cannot provide a good representation of isotherm data with a distinct plateau.

It is important to point out that the excellent results for the Elovich isotherm have been obtained by using its nonlinear form in data correlation. The linearized Elovich isotherm (Eqn (7)) should not be used to correlate adsorption data as it tends to perform poorly. On a final note, we point out that the above model comparison was performed using three loading-implicit (Elovich, Volmer, and Jossens) and two loading-explicit (Langmuir and Freundlich) isotherm models. The five isotherms were fitted to the cobalt data set by minimizing the same objective function (Eqn (1)). This was made possible by the formulation of the three loading-implicit isotherms in terms of the Lambert W function. Using the same objective function in the least-squares fitting procedure, the five isotherms were evaluated on a consistent and unbiased basis.

CONCLUSIONS

Adsorption isotherm models are usually fitted to experimental data by minimizing the difference between the observed and calculated adsorbed phase concentrations (q). This data fitting convention is somewhat cumbersome when the isotherm model is implicit in q . This study has demonstrated that certain loading-implicit isotherm models can be converted to expressions explicit in q . The loading-implicit isotherms of Elovich, Volmer, and Jossens were successfully inverted by means of the Lambert W function. Excel's Solver was used to fit the three inverted isotherms to previously published adsorption data of water contaminants. Because there is no built-in Lambert W function in Excel, a freely available add-in and an analytical approximation were used to evaluate the Lambert W function. Both methods provided regression results like those obtained with Mathematica. We hope that the findings presented here will inspire the research community to apply the Lambert W function in environmental adsorption research. It must, however, be mentioned that only certain implicit expressions with the appropriate mathematical forms can be inverted by means of the Lambert W function.

REFERENCES

- 1 Gonçalves Jr AC, Schwantes D, Braccini AL, Albornoz F, Conradi Jr É and Zimmermann J, Canola meal-derived activated biochar treated with NaOH and CO₂ as an effective tool for Cd removal. *J Chem Technol Biotechnol* **97**:87–100 (2022).
- 2 Ghanim B, Leahy JJ, O'Dwyer TF, Kwapinski W, Pembroke JT and Murnane JG, Removal of hexavalent chromium (Cr(VI)) from aqueous solution using acid-modified poultry litter-derived hydrochar: adsorption, regeneration and reuse. *J Chem Technol Biotechnol* **97**:55–66 (2022).
- 3 Encinas-Vázquez A, Quezada-Rentería JA, Cervantes FJ, Pérez-Rábago CA, Molina-Freaner FE, Pat-Espadas AM and Estrada CA, Unraveling the mechanisms of lead adsorption and ageing process on high-temperature biochar. *J Chem Technol Biotechnol* **96**:775–784 (2021).
- 4 Kemmer G and Keller S, Nonlinear least-squares data fitting in Excel spreadsheets. *Nat Protoc* **5**:267–281 (2010).
- 5 Annesini MC, Gironi F, Ruzzi M and Tomei C, Adsorption of organic compounds onto activated carbon. *Water Res* **21**:567–571 (1987).
- 6 Sorial GA, Suidan MT, Vidic RD and Maloney SW, Competitive adsorption of phenols on GAC. I: adsorption equilibrium. *J Environ Eng* **119**:1026–1043 (1993).

- 7 Lu Q and Sorial GA, Adsorption of phenolics on activated carbon—impact of pore size and molecular oxygen. *Chemosphere* **55**:671–679 (2004).
- 8 Wang R-C, Kuo C-C and Shyu C-C, Adsorption of phenols onto granular activated carbon in a liquid–solid fluidized bed. *J Chem Technol Biotechnol* **68**:187–194 (1997).
- 9 Chu KH and Tan BC, Is the Frumkin (Fowler–Guggenheim) adsorption isotherm a two- or three-parameter equation? *Colloid Interface Sci Commun* **45**:100519 (2021).
- 10 Goličnik M, On the Lambert W function and its utility in biochemical kinetics. *Biochem Eng J* **63**:116–123 (2012).
- 11 Kesisoglou I, Singh G and Nikolaou M, The Lambert function should be in the engineering mathematical toolbox. *Comput Chem Eng* **148**:107259 (2021).
- 12 Vinokurov IA and Kankare J, Kinetics of multilayer Langmuirian adsorption. *Langmuir* **18**:6789–6795 (2002).
- 13 Liu Y and Liu YJ, Biosorption isotherms, kinetics and thermodynamics. *Sep Purif Technol* **61**:229–242 (2008).
- 14 Foo KY and Hameed BH, Insights into the modeling of adsorption isotherm systems. *Chem Eng J* **156**:2–10 (2010).
- 15 Rangabhashiyam S, Anu N, Nandagopal MSG and Selvaraju N, Relevance of isotherm models in biosorption of pollutants by agricultural byproducts. *J Environ Chem Eng* **2**:398–414 (2014).
- 16 Saadi R, Saadi Z, Fazaeli R and Fard NE, Monolayer and multilayer adsorption isotherm models for sorption from aqueous media. *Korean J Chem Eng* **32**:787–799 (2015).
- 17 Al-Ghouti MA and Da'ana DA, Guidelines for the use and interpretation of adsorption isotherm models: a review. *J Hazard Mater* **393**:122383 (2020).
- 18 Wang J and Guo X, Adsorption isotherm models: classification, physical meaning, application and solving method. *Chemosphere* **258**:127279 (2020).
- 19 Dusart O, Bouabane H and Mazet M, Adsorption sur charbon actif d'acides aminés dans l'eau: détermination de paramètres d'équilibre par différentes équations. *J Chim Phys* **88**:259–270 (1991).
- 20 Ferrandon O, Bouabane H and Mazet M, Contribution à l'étude de la validité de différents modèles, utilisés lors de l'adsorption de solutés sur charbon actif. *Rev Sci Eau* **8**:183–200 (1995).
- 21 Volmer M, Thermodynamische folgerungen aus der zustandsgleichung Fur adsorbierte stoffe. *Z Phys Chem* **115**:253–261 (1925).

- 22 Jaoued-Grayaa N, Nasraoui C, Chevalier Y and Hbaieb S, Design of molecularly imprinted polymer materials relying on hydrophobic interactions. *Colloids Surf. A Physicochem. Eng. Asp.* **647**:129008 (2022).
- 23 Jossens L, Prausnitz JM, Fritz W, Schlünder EU and Myers AL, Thermodynamics of multi-solute adsorption from dilute aqueous solutions. *Chem Eng Sci* **33**:1097–1106 (1978).
- 24 Gray JJ and Tiling L, Johann Heinrich Lambert, mathematician and scientist, 1728–1777. *Hist Math* **5**:13–41 (1978).
- 25 Corless RM, Gonnet GH, Hare DEG, Jeffrey DJ and Knuth DE, On the Lambert W-function. *Adv Comput Math* **5**:329–359 (1996).
- 26 Debord J, Harel M, Bollinger J-C and Chu KH, The Elovich isotherm equation: back to the roots and new developments. (under review).
- 27 Patil SA, Patil SK, Sartape AS, Bhise SC, Vadiyar MM, Anuse MA and Kolekar SS, A *Pongamia pinnata* pods based activated carbon as an efficient scavenger for adsorption of toxic Co(II): kinetic and thermodynamic study. *Sep Sci Technol* **55**:2904–2918 (2020).
- 28 Barry DA, Parlange J-Y, Li L, Prommer H, Cunningham CJ and Stagnitti F, Analytical approximations for real values of the Lambert W-function. *Math Comput Simul* **53**:95–103 (2000).
- 29 Winitzki S, Uniform approximations for transcendental functions, in *Computational Science and its Applications – ICCSA 2003, Lecture Notes in Computer Science, Vol. 2667*, ed by Kumar V, Gavrilova ML, Tan CJK and L’Ecuyer P. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg, pp 780–789 (2003).
- 30 Scheuerell MD, An explicit solution for calculating optimum spawning stock size from Ricker’s stock recruitment model. *PeerJ* **4**:e1623 (2016).
- 31 Yu J, Feng H, Tang L, Pang Y, Wang J, Zou J, Xie Q, Liu Y, Feng C and Wang J, Insight into the key factors in fast adsorption of organic pollutants by hierarchical porous biochar. *J Hazard Mater* **403**:123610 (2021).
- 32 Zulfiqar M, Sufian S, Rabat NE and Mansor N, Enhancement of adsorption and photocatalytic activities of alkaline-based TiO₂ nanotubes for experimental and theoretical investigation under FeCl₃ and H₂O₂. *J Water Process Eng* **39**:101715 (2021).
- 33 Kumbhar P, Narale D, Bhosale R, Jambhale C, Kim J-H and Kolekar S, Synthesis of tea waste/Fe₃O₄ magnetic composite (TWMC) for efficient adsorption of crystal violet dye: isotherm, kinetic and thermodynamic studies. *J Environ Chem Eng* **10**:107893 (2022).

- 34 Meng F, Huang Q, Larson SL and Han FX, The adsorption characteristics of uranium(VI) from aqueous solution on leonardite and leonardite-derived humic acid: a comparative study. *Langmuir* **37**:12557–12567 (2021).
- 35 Inglezakis VJ, Pouloupoulos SG and Kazemian H. Insights into the S-shaped sorption isotherms and their dimensionless forms. *Microporous Mesoporous Mater* **272**:166–176 (2018).
- 36 Krishnamurti K, A new adsorption isotherm. *Proc Indian Acad Sci – Math Sci* **33**:92 (1951).
- 37 Chu KH, Fitting a little-known isotherm equation to S-shaped adsorption equilibrium data. *Sep Purif Technol* **259**:118079 (2021).
- 38 Hand DW, Herlevich Jr JA, Perram DL and Crittenden JC, Synthetic adsorbent versus GAC for TCE removal. *J Am Water Works Assoc* **86**:64–72 (1994).
- 39 Flora JRV, Suidan MT, Wuellner AM and Boyer TK, Anaerobic treatment of a simulated high-strength industrial wastewater containing chlorophenols. *Water Environ Res* **66**:21–31 (1994).
- 40 Parker Jr GR, Optimum isotherm equation and thermodynamic interpretation for aqueous 1,1,2-trichloroethene adsorption isotherms on three adsorbents. *Adsorption* **1**:113–132 (1995).
- 41 Meghea A, Rehner HH, Peleanu I and Mihalache R, Test-fitting on adsorption isotherms of organic pollutants from waste waters on activated carbon. *J Radioanal Nucl Chem* **229**:105–110 (1998).
- 42 Lu Q and Sorial GA, A comparative study of multicomponent adsorption of phenolic compounds on GAC and ACFs. *J Hazard Mater* **167**:89–96 (2009).
- 43 Srinivasan R and Sorial GA, Adsorption of geosmin and MIB on activated carbon fibers—single and binary solute system. *Water Air Soil Pollut Focus* **9**:223–235 (2009).
- 44 Yan L and Sorial GA, Chemical activation of bituminous coal for hampering oligomerization of organic contaminants. *J Hazard Mater* **197**:311–319 (2011).
- 45 Yan L and Sorial GA, Carbon activation for hampering oligomerization of phenolics in multicomponent systems. *Water Air Soil Pollut* **224**:1588 (2013).
- 46 McKay G, Otterburn MS and Aga JA, Fuller's earth and fired clay as adsorbents for dyestuffs. *Water Air Soil Pollut* **24**:307–322 (1985).
- 47 McKay G, El Geundi M and Nassar MM, Equilibrium studies during the removal of dyestuffs from aqueous solutions using bagasse pith. *Water Res* **21**:1513–1520 (1987).

- 48 Ramadoss R and Subramaniam D, Removal of divalent nickel from aqueous solution using blue-green marine algae: adsorption modeling and applicability of various isotherm models. *Sep Sci Technol* **54**:943–961 (2019).
- 49 Nayak AK and Pal A, Utilization of lignocellulosic waste for acridine orange uptake: insights into multiparameter isotherms modeling with ANN-aimed formulation. *J Environ Eng* **146**:04020096 (2020).
- 50 Chaabane L, Beyou E, El Ghali A and Baouab MHV, Comparative studies on the adsorption of metal ions from aqueous solutions using various functionalized graphene oxide sheets as supported adsorbents. *J Hazard Mater* **389**:121839 (2020).
- 51 Chaabane L, Beyou E and Baouab MHV, Preparation of a novel zwitterionic graphene oxide-based adsorbent to remove of heavy metal ions from water: modeling and comparative studies. *Adv Powder Technol* **32**:2502–2516 (2021).
- 52 Hashem A, Taha GM, Fletcher AJ, Mohamed LA and Samaha SH, Highly efficient adsorption of Cd(II) onto carboxylated camelthorn biomass: applicability of three-parameter isotherm models, kinetics, and mechanism. *J Polym Environ* **29**:1630–1642 (2021).
- 53 Itaya A, Kato N, Yamamoto J and Okamoto K, Liquid phase adsorption equilibrium of phenol and its derivatives on macroreticular adsorbents. *J Chem Eng Jpn* **17**:389–395 (1984).
- 54 Browne TE and Cohen Y, Aqueous-phase adsorption of trichloroethene and chloroform onto polymeric resins and activated carbon. *Ind Eng Chem Res* **29**:1338–1345 (1990).
- 55 Lin SH and Wu CL, Ammonia removal from aqueous solution by ion exchange. *Ind Eng Chem Res* **35**:553–558 (1996).
- 56 Lin SH, Wang CS and Chang CH, Removal of methyl *tert*-butyl ether from contaminated water by macroreticular resin. *Ind Eng Chem Res* **41**:4116–4121 (2002).
- 57 Hamdaoui O and Naffrechoux E, Modeling of adsorption isotherms of phenol and chlorophenols onto granular activated carbon. Part II. Models with more than two parameters. *J Hazard Mater* **147**:401–411 (2007).
- 58 Saravanan A, Kumar PS, Govarthanan M, George CS, Vaishnavi S, Mouliswaran B, Kumar SP, Jeevanantham S and Yaashikaa PR, Adsorption characteristics of magnetic nanoparticles coated mixed fungal biomass for toxic Cr(VI) ions in aquatic environment. *Chemosphere* **267**:129226 (2021).
- 59 Lin SH and Lin RC, Adsorption of 1,1,1,2-tetrafluoroethane by various adsorbents. *J Environ Eng* **125**:1048–1053 (1999).

- 60 Lin SH and Lin RC, Adsorption and mass transfer characteristics of pentane and cyclopentane by various adsorbents. *Environ Technol* **20**:11–19 (1999).
- 61 Kim D, Cai Z and Sorial GA, Determination of gas phase adsorption isotherms—a simple constant volume method. *Chemosphere* **64**:1362–1368 (2006).
- 62 Juang R-S, Wu F-C and Tseng R-L, Adsorption isotherms of phenolic compounds from aqueous solutions onto activated carbon fibers. *J Chem Eng Data* **41**:487–492 (1996).
- 63 Bayuo J, Abukari MA and Pelig-Ba KB, Optimization using central composite design (CCD) of response surface methodology (RSM) for biosorption of hexavalent chromium from aqueous media. *Appl Water Sci* **10**:135 (2020).
- 64 Akaike H, A new look at the statistical model identification. *IEEE Trans. Autom. Control* **19**:716–723 (1974).
- 65 Motulsky H and Christopoulos A, *Fitting Models to Biological Data Using Linear and Nonlinear Regression: A Practical Guide to Curve Fitting*. Oxford University Press, Oxford, (2004).